

EDUCATIONAL METHODS**Kakajanov Rovshen Rakhmankakaevich**

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Abstract: Organization of methods based on textbooks and their activities

Key words: "Brainstorming", "Zigzag" method, "Working in small groups", "Discussion"

The accuracy and internal logic of the lesson, its goal-orientedness caused the logic of the lesson to teach new material to a certain extent to influence the linguistic phenomenon and its linguistic essence. It is important for the teacher to be aware of this connection and gradually open it up with the students during the tasks.

Education is a cooperative activity of the teacher and students, and in this process, the development of the individual, his education and upbringing is realized. In the lessons, the teacher conveys his knowledge, skills and abilities to students through exercises, and students acquire the ability to use them as a result of mastering them. In the process of learning, students use different forms of learning, that is, they rely on specific differences in receiving, processing and applying the information being learned. In the course of education, issues of education and upbringing are solved in the form of cooperation between teachers and students during classes, independent work of students, and extracurricular activities.

The purpose of education is formed according to the needs of society. Therefore, the goal of education should be appropriate and proportionate. The goal of education in scientific literature is to create skills and competencies, develop logical-creative thinking, improve communicative literacy, inculcate the national idea, form oriental education, define personality it is emphasized that it consists of spiritual enrichment. Based on the educational goal, students' communication culture is improved by increasing their independent thinking, oral and written

literacy, and developing logical thinking. On the basis of the educational goal, spiritual, ideological and sophisticated education is provided. In the process of language learning, there is an opportunity to get closer to the cultural and moral values of the people. Today, the interest in using interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day.

One of the reasons for this is that until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, and the use of modern technologies allows them to search for the knowledge they acquire, independent study and thinking, analysis. even teaches them to draw final conclusions themselves. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance. Today, in education "Brainstorming", "Thoughtstorming", "Networks" method, "Sinquain", "BBB", "Fifth plus", "6x6x6", "Debate", "Role-playing game", Modern technologies such as FSMU, "Working in small groups", "Rounded snow", "Zigzag", "I will say the last word" are used.

"Zigzag" method

The students of the class are divided into 7 groups and the groups are named. In groups, the text explaining the essence of the new topic is divided into parts, and the task of familiarizing with the content of the separated parts is assigned to the groups. Pupils study the texts carefully and speak. In order to save time, leaders are determined from among the group members, and the noted task is performed by them. Leaders' opinions can be supplemented by group members. After the students of all groups talk about the content of the text assigned to them, the texts are exchanged between groups and the previous activity is repeated. Several texts are presented to the groups. In this way, after the contents of all the texts are studied by the groups, the students distinguish the main concepts of the studied topic, determine their logical interrelationship, and develop a scheme related to the topic based on the ideas that have arisen.

Then, on the basis of the acquired knowledge, the students themselves are given the task of developing such schemes.

It gives a positive result if it is used in lessons to repeat games and tasks or in reinforcement lessons. The choice of which type of game-task depends on the type of lesson, the level of training of students to perform games-tasks, their level of knowledge, opportunities for independent creative work, the ability to quickly recall what they have learned, and the degree to which creativity is formed.

Used literature

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